

Impact of Facilities Engineers on Building and Sustaining Effective Maintenance Culture in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The maintenance culture in Nigeria faces persistent challenges, posing a threat to the continuous functioning of critical infrastructure crucial for economic growth. This study seeks to investigate the unique contributions of facilities engineers in establishing and maintaining an effective maintenance culture in Nigeria. The urgency arises from shortcomings in current practices and the essential role played by facilities engineers in ensuring the durability and efficiency of infrastructure vital for economic growth. The research objective is to evaluate the impact of facilities engineers on the development and sustenance of an effective maintenance culture. A well-structured online questionnaire was developed and administered to 370 respondents, including facilities engineers, managers, and other professionals involved in infrastructure maintenance. The findings uncover a significant correlation between the proactive strategies implemented by facilities engineers and the effectiveness of maintenance culture. By highlighting the critical role of facilities engineers in establishing a resilient maintenance culture, the study charts a course for stakeholders to foster sustainable practices and advance towards infrastructure excellence. It advocates focused efforts to acknowledge and leverage the influence of facilities engineers, ensuring the durability and efficiency of Nigeria's indispensable infrastructures.

Keywords: Facilities engineers, infrastructure, maintenance culture, Nigeria, proactive strategies, sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, the effective maintenance of vital infrastructure, including transportation networks, energy facilities, healthcare systems, educational institutions, and communication networks, significantly depends on the role of facilities engineers (Emily & Muyengwa, 2021). However, despite their critical importance, maintaining these systems effectively remains a formidable challenge (Salim & Negara, 2018). Historically, Nigeria has struggled with prioritising the construction phase of projects over their long-term maintenance, as highlighted in recent research (Adhlakun et al., 2022). This approach has perpetuated a cycle of neglect, where infrastructure assets rapidly deteriorate due to insufficient attention to upkeep, echoing findings in the literature (Alshboul et al., 2023; Argyroudis et al., 2019). The consequences of this neglect are profound, impacting both the economy and the well-being of the populace. Infrastructure failures lead to decreased productivity, increased operational costs for businesses, and disruptions in service delivery, as evidenced by recent studies (Adhlakun et al., 2020). Moreover, such failures pose risks to public safety and contribute to a decline in the overall quality of life for citizens.

To address these challenges, the role of facilities engineers emerges as pivotal. By implementing proactive maintenance strategies and fostering a culture of upkeep, facilities engineers play a crucial role in sustaining infrastructure assets throughout their lifecycle (Johannes et al., 2021). Their expertise is crucial for identifying potential issues, implementing preventive measures, and

ensuring the efficient functioning of infrastructure systems. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) also offer a promising avenue for leveraging the expertise of facilities engineers in infrastructure maintenance (Zhang et al., 2024). By collaborating with the private sector, facilities engineers can access additional resources and technical expertise to effectively address maintenance challenges. However, effective regulation and oversight are essential to safeguarding the public interest in such partnerships.

A. The importance of maintenance culture in Nigeria

The significance of maintenance culture in Nigeria cannot be overstated, as it plays a crucial role in sustaining infrastructure integrity, promoting economic development, and ensuring the well-being of its citizens. Maintenance culture encompasses the attitudes, behaviours, and practices that prioritise the continuous care and preservation of infrastructure assets (Adelakun, 2022; Kolawole et al., 2023; Lamond & Everett, 2019). In Nigeria, developing a strong maintenance culture is crucial for several reasons:

- i. **Infrastructure Sustainability:** A strong maintenance culture is fundamental to ensuring the longevity and functionality of infrastructure assets. Regular maintenance activities, such as inspections, repairs, and upgrades, help prevent deterioration and prolong the lifespan of critical infrastructure components (Achillopoulou et al., 2020). By maintaining infrastructure in optimal condition, Nigeria can avoid costly repairs and replacements in the long run.
- ii. **Economic Growth:** Infrastructure plays a central role in driving economic growth by providing essential services, facilitating commerce, and supporting industrial activities. However, poorly maintained infrastructure hampers economic productivity and competitiveness. In contrast, a proactive maintenance culture enhances operational efficiency, minimizes downtime, and attracts investment, thereby fostering economic development and job creation.
- iii. **Public Safety and Well-Being:** Neglected infrastructure poses significant risks to public safety and health. Malfunctioning transportation systems, unreliable power grids, and inadequate healthcare facilities can jeopardise lives and exacerbate societal challenges. By prioritising maintenance culture, Nigeria can ensure the reliability and safety of its infrastructure assets, thereby safeguarding the well-being of its citizens.
- iv. **Environmental Sustainability:** Effective maintenance practices contribute to environmental sustainability by minimising resource consumption, reducing waste generation, and mitigating environmental impacts. Regular maintenance helps optimize energy efficiency, reduce emissions, and conserve natural resources, aligning with Nigeria's commitments to sustainable development and climate action.
- v. **Reputation and Image:** A well-maintained infrastructure network enhances Nigeria's reputation on the global stage and instills confidence among investors, tourists, and international partners. Conversely, persistent infrastructure failures and service disruptions tarnish Nigeria's image, deter foreign investment, and hinder its ability to attract skilled professionals and resources.

B. Role of Facilities Engineers

Facilities engineers play a pivotal role in establishing and maintaining an effective maintenance culture in Nigeria (Ugwu et al., 2018). Their expertise, skills, and responsibilities significantly

contribute to the management and preservation of critical infrastructure assets across various sectors. The role of facilities engineers can be outlined as follows:

- i. **Infrastructure Management:** Facilities engineers are responsible for overseeing the management of infrastructure assets throughout their lifecycle, from design and construction to operation and maintenance (Pilanawithana & Sandanayake, 2017). They ensure that infrastructure projects are implemented according to specifications, standards, and regulatory requirements, thereby laying the foundation for sustainable maintenance practices.
- ii. **Preventive Maintenance Planning:** Facilities engineers develop and implement preventive maintenance plans to proactively address potential issues and minimize the risk of equipment failure or system breakdowns. By conducting routine inspections, predictive maintenance analyses, and scheduling maintenance activities, maintenance professionals help identify and address maintenance needs before they escalate into costly problems.
- iii. **Troubleshooting and Problem-Solving:** When infrastructure assets experience issues or malfunctions, facilities engineers are tasked with diagnosing the root causes of problems and implementing effective solutions (Ghaffarianhoseini et al., 2017). Their technical expertise enables them to troubleshoot complex systems, identify faulty components, and coordinate repair efforts to restore functionality and minimise disruptions.
- iv. **Performance Optimisation:** Facilities engineers aim to enhance the performance of infrastructure assets by implementing efficiency measures, upgrading outdated systems, and integrating new technologies. They analyze operational data, evaluate asset performance, and recommend improvements to enhance reliability, productivity, and cost-effectiveness.
- v. **Compliance and Safety:** Facilities engineers ensure that infrastructure assets comply with relevant regulations, codes, and safety standards to protect public health and safety. They conduct risk assessments, implement safety protocols, and oversee regulatory compliance to minimize hazards and prevent accidents in the workplace.
- vi. **Stakeholder Collaboration:** Facilities engineers collaborate with various stakeholders, including government agencies, contractors, vendors, and end-users, to coordinate maintenance activities, allocate resources effectively, and address emerging challenges. Their ability to communicate effectively and build partnerships fosters a culture of collaboration and accountability in the maintenance process.

C. Research Objective

The primary objective of this research is to investigate the impact of facilities engineers on the development and sustainability of an effective maintenance culture in Nigeria. The study aims to achieve the following research objectives:

- To examine the strategies employed by facilities engineers in establishing and maintaining an effective maintenance culture in Nigeria.
- To assess the correlation between the proactive strategies implemented by facilities engineers and the effectiveness of maintenance culture in Nigeria.
- To explore the implications of facilities engineers' contributions for sustainable infrastructure management and economic development in Nigeria.

By addressing these research objectives, the study aims to enhance understanding of the role played by facilities engineers in fostering a culture of proactive maintenance and its implications for infrastructure resilience, economic growth, and societal well-being in Nigeria. Additionally, the research aims to provide valuable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and academic researchers to inform decision-making processes, promote best practices, and drive positive change in the maintenance culture landscape.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents in Infrastructure Maintenance

Variable		Frequency (n = 370)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	268	72.43
	Female	102	27.57
Age	Below 25	23	6.22
	25 - 35	60	16.22
	36 - 45	164	44.32
	Above 45	123	33.24
Educational Qualification	Technical Certificate	24	6.49
	Professional Certification	55	14.86
	Higher National Diploma (HND)	64	17.30
	Bachelor's Degree	86	23.24
	Post Graduate Degree	123	33.24
	Ph.D. or other advanced degree	18	4.86
Years of Experience in Infrastructure Maintenance	Less than 1 year	28	7.57
	1 - 5 years	62	16.76
	6 - 10 years	126	34.05
	More than 10 years	154	41.62

Table 1 presents demographic data for 370 respondents, detailing gender distribution, age groups, educational qualifications, and years of experience in infrastructure maintenance. The majority were male, comprising 72.43% of the sample. The largest age group was 36-45, representing 44.32%. Bachelor's degrees were the most common educational qualification at 23.24%, while over 10 years of experience in infrastructure maintenance was reported by 41.62% of respondents.

D. Strategies Employed by Facilities Engineers

- i. **Preventive Maintenance Programmes:** Engineers carefully plan and execute these routines to minimise unexpected failures and downtime, ensuring smooth operations. Proactive checks preempt potential issues, saving costs and preventing disruptions in critical systems. By adhering to these programmes, facility engineers uphold reliability standards, prolong equipment life, and ensure operational continuity, which is vital in industries reliant on uninterrupted functionality.

- ii. **Training and development of staff:** This involves imparting specialised skills and knowledge to maintenance personnel. Through workshops, seminars, and on-the-job training, engineers equip their teams with the expertise needed to address complex challenges efficiently. Well-trained staff not only enhance productivity but also contribute to a culture of continuous improvement. Investing in the development of employees fosters loyalty, boosts morale, and cultivates a skilled workforce capable of adapting to evolving technologies and industry standards. Ultimately, this investment pays dividends in the form of enhanced performance, reduced errors, and increased innovation.
- iii. **Predictive maintenance technologies:** This leverage data analytics and sensor technology to forecast equipment failures before they occur. By analysing trends and patterns in machine behaviour, engineers can anticipate issues and take proactive measures to mitigate them. This predictive approach minimises downtime and maintenance costs while maximising equipment reliability and performance. Adopting predictive maintenance transforms reactive practices into proactive strategies, enabling organisations to schedule maintenance activities strategically, optimise resource allocation, and extend asset lifespans. The result is enhanced operational efficiency, reduced downtime, and improved bottom-line performance.
- iv. **Maintenance management software:** This streamlines the organisation and execution of maintenance activities. Engineers use sophisticated software platforms to schedule tasks, track inventory, and generate reports. This centralised system enhances communication, facilitates data-driven decision-making, and improves overall efficiency in managing maintenance operations. By digitising and automating routine tasks, maintenance management software frees up valuable time for engineers to focus on strategic planning and problem-solving. Real-time visibility into maintenance activities enables proactive identification of bottlenecks and inefficiencies, leading to continuous improvement and enhanced performance across the organisation.
- v. **Collaboration with other departments:** This fosters synergy and alignment across different areas of the organization. Engineers work closely with operations, finance, and other departments to coordinate maintenance efforts with broader business objectives. By sharing resources, expertise, and insights, cross-departmental collaboration optimises resource allocation, enhances problem-solving capabilities, and promotes a holistic approach to infrastructure management. Collaborative endeavours break down silos, encourage knowledge sharing, and promote a culture of teamwork and innovation. Ultimately, this integrated approach drives efficiency, reduces costs, and maximises the overall impact of facilities engineering on organisational success.

Table 2: Effectiveness of Maintenance Culture Ratings

Scale		Frequency (n = 370)	Percentage (%)
Effectiveness of Maintenance Culture	Very effective	34	9.19
	Effective	58	15.68
	Neutral	35	9.46
	Ineffective	141	38.11
	Very ineffective	102	27.57

The data from Table 2 shows that the majority of respondents perceive a lack of effectiveness in the maintenance culture. Combined, the percentages of those who rated it as "ineffective" or "very ineffective" (65.68%) outweigh those who found it "very effective" or "effective" (24.87%). This disparity underscores a prevailing sentiment among respondents regarding deficiencies in the current maintenance practices, highlighting the need for improvement and reform.

E. Implications for Sustainable Infrastructure Management and Economic Development:

- i. Sustainable infrastructure management:** This involves adopting practices that balance the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. By prioritising durability, efficiency, and environmental responsibility, engineers ensure that infrastructure projects contribute to long-term viability. Sustainable management practices reduce resource consumption, minimise environmental degradation, and promote resilience in the face of climate change. Embracing sustainability principles in infrastructure development safeguards natural resources, enhances quality of life, and fosters a legacy of responsible stewardship for future generations to inherit.
- ii. Economic development:** This hinges on the creation of infrastructure that facilitates growth, innovation, and prosperity. Engineers play a pivotal role in designing and implementing projects that stimulate economic activity, attract investment, and improve living standards. Infrastructure investments in transportation, energy, and telecommunications networks foster connectivity, efficiency, and competitiveness in global markets. By enhancing access to markets, education, and healthcare, infrastructure development stimulates job creation, increases productivity, and drives economic growth. A robust infrastructure framework is essential for attracting businesses, supporting industry expansion, and unlocking the full economic potential of a region.
- iii. Environmental sustainability:** This involves minimising the ecological footprint, conserving natural resources, and mitigating environmental impact. Engineers integrate eco-friendly design principles, renewable energy sources, and green technologies to reduce carbon emissions and preserve biodiversity (Adelakun & Olanipekun, 2019; Olanipekun & Adelakun, 2020). Sustainable infrastructure projects prioritise energy efficiency, waste reduction, and pollution prevention, promoting a healthier environment for current and future generations (Adelakun, 2024; Okoye & Adelakun, 2019). By embracing sustainability, engineers contribute to global efforts to combat climate change, protect ecosystems, and ensure the long-term health of the planet. Environmental stewardship in infrastructure development safeguards natural habitats, preserves ecological balance, and fosters harmony between human activities and the environment.
- iv. Social impact:** This encompasses the effects on communities, societies, and individuals. Engineers strive to design projects that enhance accessibility, equity, and inclusivity, ensuring that infrastructure benefits are shared equitably among all segments of society. Socially responsible infrastructure investments prioritise community engagement, cultural sensitivity, and social inclusion, empowering marginalised groups and fostering social cohesion. Infrastructure projects that enhance access to education, healthcare, and basic services uplift communities, alleviate poverty, and improve quality of life. By prioritising social impact, engineers contribute to building resilient, vibrant, and inclusive societies where everyone has the opportunity to thrive.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research emphasises the significant impact of facilities engineers on establishing and maintaining an effective maintenance culture in Nigeria. The demographic analysis revealed a predominantly male workforce, primarily aged between 36-45 years, holding bachelor's degrees or higher qualifications, indicating a well-educated and experienced workforce. Facilities engineers use various strategies, including preventive maintenance programmes, staff training, predictive maintenance technologies, management software, and collaboration with other departments. These strategies were identified as key contributors to the effectiveness of maintenance culture, enhancing operational efficiency, and promoting proactive maintenance approaches. However, the perceived effectiveness of maintenance culture varied among respondents, indicating a need for continuous improvement and innovation in maintenance practices. Furthermore, facility engineers' contributions have significant implications for sustainable infrastructure management and economic development. Sustainable practices promote resilience and reduce environmental impact, while infrastructure development drives economic growth and improves living standards. Overall, this research highlights the vital role of facilities engineers in shaping maintenance culture, promoting sustainability, and driving economic development in Nigeria. It emphasises the importance of investing in infrastructure and fostering innovation and collaboration to address complex challenges in the infrastructure sector.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. By promoting diversity and encouraging gender diversity in facilities engineering.
- ii. Through continuous training and providing ongoing professional development for engineers.
- iii. By investing in predictive technology and increasing investment in predictive maintenance technologies.
- iv. By using maintenance software and implementing robust maintenance management software.
- v. fostering interdepartmental collaboration and promoting cooperation across departments.
- vi. By embracing continuous improvement and fostering a culture of ongoing enhancement in maintenance practices.
- vii. By adopting sustainable practices and integrating sustainable infrastructure management practices.

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